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Mental Asylum as a Social and Political Metaphor in the Cinema from the Two Sides of the Iron Curtain¹

Abstract: *Applying comparative analysis, the article examines the usage of the mental health institution in two emblematic for American and Bulgarian Cinema films – “One Flew Over the Cuckoo’s Nest” and “Adaptation”. Despite the fact that the movies were produced in quite different social and cultural contexts, their contents reveal analogous critical messages addressed to society during the 1970s: the system tries to dominate by making some extraordinary individuals obey the common rules.*

Keywords: *American Cinema; Bulgarian Cinema; mental asylum.*

From its emergence, cinema discovers the realm of mysteries connected to mental disorders and not surprisingly the latter turned out an everlasting source of plots and personages whose charm fires the popular imagination up to date. According to Adam Fisher (2016), the earliest on-screen portrayal of a character with mental health issues was identified in the silent film *Trilly and Little Billee* directed by George Du Mourier in 1896. It was not until a decade later, in 1906, that a mental institution was represented the first time in the movie *Dr. Dippy’s Sanitarium* (Fisher 2016; Brtivić, Vuković, Zlopaša, Zebić, Damjanović 2012: 78), which marks the emergence of an enormous corpus of films dealing with various aspects of mental health care. Moreover, this impressive body of works fomented discontent among professionals belonging to the field (psychiatrists, psychotherapists and psychologists) because they strongly believe that cinema produces numerous misunderstandings and misconceptions in terms of mental disorders and their treatment. The most significant enquiry raised by scholars from the domain of media concerns the fundamental problem of cinema and TV channels generating solid

¹ The present paper has been produced within the framework of the research project *Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good* (LEVIATHAN). The project is funded by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (ERC Synergy Grant No. 854503).

stereotypes about the mental health sector, and asks about the ways in which circulating representations affect public attitudes and ‘colonize’ the spectators’ fantasy. Drawing on accumulated empirical studies, researchers (Diefenbach & West 2007; Thornton & Wahl 1996; Kimmerle & Cress 2013) reveal a clear correlation between negative images and prejudices towards mental illnesses which leads to a process of heavy stigmatization of patients suffering from mental disorders. Further, this stigma easily broadens its territory encompasses therapists and mental health institutions *per se*.

In his frequently quoted article, George Domino explores the huge influence that the globally acclaimed American movie *One Flew Over the Cuckoo’s Nest* (1975) exerted on audiences’ views (Domino 1983). Exploring the attitude shifts over the course of an experiment in which college students participate as questionnaire respondents, Domino demonstrates the noticeable impact of the film on the spectators’ minds and emotional reactions immediately after the screening. Students who have watched the movie express more negative attitudes compared to those who did not present at the projection. Since the 1980s and even earlier cinematic portrayal of the mental health sector has been carefully scrutinized and discussed. However what is crucially important, and I would like to emphasize, is that mental health institutions could be read in a wider political and social context as a metaphor for the specific society of a particular historical epoch. This becomes particularly evident when applying principles of comparative analysis to the study of phenomena situated in seemingly different cultural settings.

In the following exposition, I will examine in detail two emblematic (for their respective national cinemas) fiction films created in the USA and Bulgaria during the 1970s: *One Flew Over the Cuckoo’s Nest* (1975)² and *Adaptation* (1979)³.

My choice of these titles stems from the following facts: first, the process of the practical realization of the films was highly complex as these projects provoked subversive messages and allusions which were

² *One Flew Over Cuckoo’s Nest* (1975, USA) – director: Miloš Forman, screenplay: Lawrence Hauben, Bo Goldman based on the novel by Ken Kesey, cinematography: Haskell Wexler, Bill Butler, music: Jack Nitzsche, producers: Saul Zaentz, Michael Douglas – Fantasy Films, starring: Jack Nicholson, Louise Fletcher, William Redfield.

³ *Adaptation/Adaptatsia* (1979, 1981 Bulgaria) – director: Vulo Radev, script: Rayna Tomova and Vulo Radev, cinematography: Hristo Totev, music: Mitko Shterev, producer: Bulgarian National Television, starring: Eli Skorcheva, Antoni Genov, Ivan Grigorov, Nikolay Sotirov.

highly unacceptable for Hollywood studios and for State authorities; this explains the strong resistance they faced. Second, these films could be regarded as unique visual documents of the historical periods in which they were made and the mental asylum was used as a deliberate metaphor for their respective societies – American and Bulgarian – on opposite sides of the Iron Curtain.⁴ Through this approach, their authors effectively conveyed fair critiques of the symptomatic issues of their time. Thirdly, the level of popularity reached within their countries was remarkable (*One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest* also achieved incredible international visibility) and it was a testimony to the public's ability to engage with the deepest layers of the filmic text. Finally, both works belong to their national cinematic canons today and symbolize important milestones in the professional career of their directors (Miloš Forman and Vulo Radev).

One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest: The Story Behind the Film

If any film has made an epitome of mental asylum's celluloid depiction, undoubtedly, it is the American classic *One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest* (1975), directed by Miloš Forman. The movie catapulted the Czech immigrant to international stardom during the 48th ceremony of the American Academy held on 29th March 1976 when it became the night's big winner after receiving the five most prominent Oscars in the categories Best Film, Best Director, Best Screenplay, Best Actress, and Best Actor.

The story behind this fantastic and unexpected success is truly amazing. In his autobiography *Turnaround: A Memoir*, Miloš Forman in partnership with his co-author Jan Novak craft an exciting narrative of the events surrounding this long-cherished project.

As is well known, in the 1960s, Miloš Forman was part of the so-called 'New Czech Wave' along with other great authors such as Vera Chytilova, Juri Menzel, Ivan Passer, Jan Nemeč. The promising young filmmaker received the Grand Prix at the festival in Locarno for his debut *Black Peter* (1963) in a competition that included Michelangelo Antonioni and Jean-Luc Godard. His second film *The Love of a Blonde* (1965) was nominated for an Oscar in the Best Foreign Film category (Форман, Новак 1995: 188-189, 205).

Irrespective of the quite complex interaction in the sphere of cultural relations between the West and the countries from the Soviet bloc,

⁴ For more detail on the history and development of psychiatry in Bulgaria, see Атанасов, Станчев (2013).

there were some forms of mutual exchange. For example in the 1960s the celebrated superstar of Hollywood – Kirk Douglas made a trip to Czechoslovakia and during his stay in Prague, the American actor met Miloš Forman. Douglas was deeply impressed by the films by the Czech director and shared with him that he was working on a new project based on a novel. At the end of their conversation, the American actor promised to send the book by mail so that he could familiarise himself with its content. The novel was *One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest* by Ken Kesey and for the next ten years Kirk Douglas did his best to find a studio willing to produce a film adaptation. Hollywood tycoons rejected his idea citing their reluctance to invest financial resources in a project centred around a mental health institution (Форман, Новак 1995: 275-276). The real reason, however, may have been the general attitude of the mental health professionals who viewed Ken Kesey's literary work as extremely denigrating and malicious.

Fig. 1. Jack Nicholson, Louise Fletcher, Michael Douglas and Saul Zaentz at the night of the Oscars⁵

Having waited a couple of months, Miloš Forman was profoundly disappointed because he never received the book. A decade later when he immigrated to the USA, two producers – Michael Douglas and Saul Zaentz came across him and offered the same project. Forman was thrilled and immediately accepted their proposal. However, at a party at

⁵ Sources: Getty Images.

the Douglas family house, the Czech director encountered Kirk Douglas again. The American legend reacted fiercely accusing Forman of being ungrateful because he didn't bother to respond after receiving the book. At that moment the Eastern European immigrant realised what had really happened: the parcel had been confiscated by the Secret Service. Despite this, Forman's fate was already decided: he seized the opportunity to make the film, thanks to the new producers (Форман, Новак 1995: 273-276).

The realization of the project was an enormous challenge. A serious obstacle arose when the psychiatric hospitals throughout the country refused, one after another, to provide locations for the movie, in other words, they were reluctant to cooperate with the team. The only hospital head who agreed to participate was Dr. Dean Brooke (head of the State Mental Hospital in Eugene, Oregon). However, he imposed a crucial condition: his patients had to be included in the film as he was absolutely convinced that it would improve their self-confidence and social skills. The patients indeed participated in the movie, and what is more, Dr. Brooke himself played the role of the hospital director – which could be interpreted as a cameo role, even though his character was named Dr. John Spivay (Форман, Новак 1995: 279-290).

The film tells the story of Randle Patrick McMurphy, performed brilliantly by Jack Nicholson, a petty crook who simulates a mental disease so as to avoid prison for minor crimes. He succeeds in his plan and is interned in a psychiatric institution. However, his rebellious personality soon drives him to deliberately violate the hospital's order and routine. McMurphy disputes the established rules and even openly encourages his fellow patients to reject them, leading to a face-to-face dramatic confrontation with the omnipresent tyrant Nurse Ratched, who is obsessed by the compulsive conception about the strict regulation.

The character experiences various forms of abusive treatment. Initially, he attempts to avoid taking the prescribed pills but his provocative acts and increasing resistance pose a serious threat to the order within the mental institution. As a consequence, McMurphy is subjected to electroshock therapy and lobotomized, destroying his will and any ability to think rationally.

It is worth noting that some scholars, such as Beatriz Vera Poseck, highlight the specific portrayal of the hospital:

The asylum scenario portrays a labyrinth of corridors and rooms, full of barriers, doors, locks and ties that starkly reflect feelings of repression, control and fear. In this film, the mental institution is converted

into a repressive agent utilized by a society bent on breaking the creativity of free spirits. The film perpetuates the myth that asylums are places where one can enter but never leave and in which the aim is not to cure but to subjugate and alienate the inmates. The role of the demon psychiatrist mentioned above is in this case especially explicit. (Poseck 2007: 67).

Fig. 2. *One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest*, 1975⁶

While Poseck overtly criticizes the film, disagreeing with its pattern of depiction of both patients and mental health professionals and their practices, what she overlooks is that the novel and later the film extend beyond the confines of issues to do with the field of mental disorders. Ken Kesey's world famous book, written in 1962, certainly reflects the political and social context of its time, when the Vietnam War sparked protests and a burgeoning anti-war movement. During this period, especially after 1964, mental institutions and psychiatry were viewed highly negatively as a repressive mechanism of control used by the establishment (Gabbard & Gabbard 1999). Logically, Miloš Forman preserves this characteristic of the novel constructing a dark representation of

⁶ Sources: Great Big Canvas.

1970s American society, with the subversive suggestion that there is no place for extraordinary, freedom-loving individuals.

Adaptation: The Story Behind the Film

On the other side of the world, the prominent Bulgarian filmmaker Vulo Radev created his film *Adaptation* (1979, 1981) marking the first time in Bulgarian Cinema that topics intimately linked to the psychoanalysis and psychotherapy's practices were explored. Although that the film was well received by the public, it turned out to be Radev's last project. Authorities silently disapproved of *Adaptation*. The film was produced in 1979 and although Vulo Radev was a well-established author, socially visible and of a good standing within the cultural elite, according to various testimonies, the film was suspended for a while⁷ (Atanasov 2003; Грозев 2021: 123-124; Владимирова 2023; Панайотов 2016). Interestingly, Radev never mentioned this issue in his memoir *Lost Spaces*, and neither did his wife Zheni Radeva in her memoirs.

The original script, written by Rayna Tomova, captivated Vulo Radev, leading him to make the film. The story brings the spectators into a psychiatric hospital in Sofia, where the young Dr. Vladimir Bankov (played by Antony Genov) organizes the first therapeutic groups to help his patients – predominantly young people struggling to fit into society. One day appears Veronika Kostova – a gifted musician traumatised during her formative years, who would start a fire whenever she would feel unable to cope with her trauma. Veronika reluctantly joins the group and tragically falls in love with Dr. Bankov, who is later accused of unethical behavior by another psychiatrist – Dr. Engiozov – an ambitious and conservative careerist who rejects the new Western methods in mental health care. The film's conclusion is open-ended, leaving the public to speculate about the fate of Dr. Bankov (particularly whether he stays in the hospital or he is dismissed), while Veronika leaves the institution, perhaps to restart her life as a pianist.

Dr. Bankov was inspired by the real-life Dr. Georgi Kamenov (1942 – 2006) who introduced innovative therapeutic practices in Bulgaria, and whose work attracted the attention of the State Security Service. Dr. Kamenov consulted the film team during the process of making it but left for Austria unexpectedly, to later spend some time in Western Germany and finally settle in the USA, where he continued to work as a psychiatrist in New York. Dr. Kamenov's name was removed from the

⁷ Central state archive, f. 1475, inv. 1, a.u. 88, p. 19.

film's credits, and his work was deliberately and entirely forgotten, as noted by his disciple Zhenyia Georgieva in a recent interview (Владимирова 2023). The film was completed in 1979 and aired on television but was not shown in cinemas until 1981, likely due to the political implications of Dr. Georgi Kamenov's departure, thus putting the film on the hold for a short period.

One of the most devoted students and participants in the Friday meetings organized by Dr. Kamenov was Philip Dimitrov⁸ – a former Prime Minister of Bulgaria after 1989 – who remarked: “Adaptation was the breakthrough that legitimized our activity. Until then nobody dared to speak publicly about group therapy. It happened during the late 1970s when we could smell freedom, we didn't possess it but it was in the air” (Владимирова 2023, Атанасов, Станчев 2013).

Fig. 3. Eli Skorcheva (Veronika) in *Adaptation* (1979, 1981)⁹

Adaptation provoked political tension and Vulo Radev was interrogated by the Commission of Culture under the Central Committee of the

⁸ Philip Dimitrov was a Prime Minister of Bulgaria in the period from November 8, 1991 to December 30, 1992, and is of a right wing political persuasion. Today Philip Dimitrov is a member of the Constitutional Court of Bulgaria.

⁹ Sources: Impressio – Dir.bg.

Bulgarian Communist Party. He was asked to explain why his film did not adhere to the normative aesthetics of socialist realism (Atanassov 2003, Георгиев, Георгиева 2006, Владимирова 2023). The themes of the topic and Dr. Kamenov's activities sparked significant anxiety among authorities. Interestingly, a similar attitude and attempts at crude intervention in the work of psychiatrists and psychologists were observed in the United States too.

Many right-wing American politicians viewed the introduction of therapeutic groups in American education with suspicion. On April 9 1969, Allan Stayng wrote in *The Review of the News* that these groups were "an attempt at involving students in Nazi and socialist models of upbringing". On January 19, 1970, Senator Ed Dickman Junior stated before Congress that the "National Association of Education participates in a plot to build a nightmare network of groups, similar to the groups constructed by the political regimes in Vietnam, Russia and China" (Панайотов, 2016).

What was most terrible in the group therapy practice in the eyes of Bulgarian authorities was that it easily slipped out of the control exerted by the bureaucratic machine, and what was even more frightful: this approach encouraged the patients to express themselves spontaneously. The key concept in the so-called '*nondirective therapy*', introduced by Dr. Kamenov and illustrated in *Adaptation*, suggested that a good therapist does not lead the patients but supports them. The psychotherapist working with groups should possess deep empathy to understand his or her patients from their point of view and reject to speak from the position of power.

Unsurprisingly, the professional guild of psychiatrists reacted with anger. In an interview conducted on April 28, 1979, Dr. Taniya Ushurumova spoke about the deep confusion expressed by her colleagues after watching the film and their hard conviction that the film presented psychiatry in a negative light (Стаматова 1979). Her testimony is highly valuable because Dr. Ushurumova confirmed that the method of group therapy is relatively unknown in Bulgaria and only in the Medical Academy in Sofia were there training courses which introduce it. Reflecting on the emotional atmosphere, she admitted to her own negative response after reading the initial version of the script, seeing it as an affront to the group therapy method, which was just beginning to gain traction in the

country. This core idea of the film was interpreted by political censors¹⁰ as a subtle critique of the system and an appeal for change. In a society where everybody is expected to follow strict regulations, any expression of individuality and spontaneity could be deemed a deviation (Панайотов, 2016, Грозев 2021).

The Point of Intersection

There is evidence in Vulo Radev's book *Lost Spaces* that he had seen *One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest* at the festival in Belgrade in February 1976 while he was working on *Adaptation* (Radev 2001: 270). I have not come across any explicit statement that Miloš Forman's film had served as a source of inspiration. However at the level of the filmic texts, some inter-textual references to the American or Czechoslovak realities could be identified. For example, when Professor Shtarbanov asks Veronika what troubles her, she unexpectedly answers: '*Ask the war and Vietnam*'; another psychiatrist explains that in Czechoslovakia (Forman's homeland), patients with mental disorders recover in their own everyday environments, and the audience is informed that Dr. Bankov has been to Prague. Additional curious details alluding to connections between the two films is that Antony Genov (Dr. Bankov) plays the part of Billy in a theatrical production directed by Krasimir Spasov in 1980, and the character Kostadin (played by Nikolay Sotirov) in *Adaptation* bears a striking resemblance to Billy. Two boys have a similar profile and personal stories: they are both self-conscious and extremely sensitive young men raised by their single mothers, and struggle with communication. Both made suicide attempts: Billy dies but Kostadin is saved by Dr. Bankov and Veronika and their tragic gestures were motivated by the humiliation they had experienced in the hospital, a microcosm of broader society.

At first glance, there is nothing in common between *One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest* and *Adaptation*: the protagonists are dramatically opposite – on one side, an introverted female pianist coming from a good family, and on the other – an extroverted male drifter with a dark past. However, both characters instigate events that reveal not only hypothetical conditions of mental health institutions during specific historical pe-

¹⁰ I do not mean here film critics, their reviews discussing *Adaptation* were favourable and they noted the artistic merit of the film. The problem is that in many cases the conversations between artists and the representatives of the political regime were not recorded officially and in such cases scholars rely heavily on the testimonies made by the events' witnesses.

riods but also serve as powerful social and political metaphors carrying mirror messages: any social and political system puts pressure and even destroys individuals who refuse to obey the rules.

Fig. 4. Eli Skorcheva (Veronika) and Dr. Bankov (Antony Genov) in *Adaptation* (1979, 1981)¹¹

The representation of the group therapy practice is a crucial mechanism at the level of the narrative structures in both movies: in *One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest*, the patients are led by the notorious Nurse Ratched – pure embodiment of the perfect system – who demonstrates her power and supremacy at every opportunity. The obvious lack of human compassion deprives the therapeutic method of its essence – to support the patients in their suffering. As already mentioned, the film reflects the turbulent context of the Vietnam War and the prevailing sentiment in American society at that time. In contrast, *Adaptation* features a group of young girls and boys who trust Dr. Bankov and believe in his innovative

¹¹ Sources: Impressio – Dir.bg.

therapeutic approach. He does not dominate the group and a different member of the group is chosen to lead each session. Another important difference lies in the status of the patients: in *One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest*, all patients are institutionalized, confined to the hospital, whereas in *Adaptation* some of them are institutionalized but others come for the sessions voluntarily and while maintaining their lives outside (Панайотов 2016). The threat in this case comes from the psychiatrists who disapprove of the new methods, preferring to preserve the status quo and its inherent power hierarchy.

The conflicts in the films are symmetrical: main characters Veronika/McMurphy clash with the informal or formal leaders – Nurse Ratched and Dr. Bankov and the conflict ends with a literal or metaphorical departure (Veronika leaves the hospital but McMurphy finds his death there). The dynamics of the confrontations reveal important facets of society (American/Bulgarian) and the mechanisms used to maintain their existing systems.

In summary, I would like to conclude that these two the context of their epoch and about the societies they depict when they are explored comparatively films reveal much more about. Such a method allows us to note the dynamic process of mutual exchange between the West and the Soviet bloc and demonstrates that the political landscape was far from black-and-white, on the contrary, these opposing regimes sometimes produced remarkably similar messages in the realm of cinema.

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